

Droneport: From Concept To Prototype

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Abstract—The paper deals with the development of an experimental mechatronic system for battery management of drones called Droneport. It was developed as an automatic system with battery swapping and recharging feature set outside the drone, allowing a quick return to a mission. The first part presents its mechanical design, installed instrumentation and software environment. The next section is dedicated to the description of the individual hardware components, highlighting particular problems that had to be solved to optimize the size, weight and fulfill robustness demands. The last section summarizes our observations regarding the contribution of this tool to the drone or UAV autonomy in general.

Index Terms—drone, battery, UAV, UAS, manipulator, swap, drone in the box

I. INTRODUCTION

These days, drones overmaster the air through various operational tasks that do not need personal supervision directly. The operational time of these flying machines is far cheaper than any other possible alternatives, which creates one of the biggest advantages.

The majority of drones are powered by lithium based batteries that provide a maximum flight time in the order of tens of minutes. In contrast to ground vehicles, the bigger battery does not mean a longer working time. Adding the capacity means adding the weight to the flying machine, which always ends up in some compromises on maximum take-off weight, limits of power consumption or build up options, as written for example in [1], [2]. Only the power density can significantly affect the flight time. There exists some developments working on better batteries [3], but they are not spread enough in these days to rely on.

In some cases, the tethering with a power station can be the option [4], [5]. Unfortunately, in most applications, the drones cannot be physically connected to the ground for a constant power replenishment due to limitations on the operational area or overcoming the maximum takeoff weight of the system.

One option to keep the drone operational is to recharge its battery, which can be done automatically without human involvement [6], [7]. That solution requires the drone to stop working for long periods of time, sit on the ground and block the charging station for other drones. So, this option is suitable for single drone systems where drone working time can be divided into given intervals without affecting the operational goals. Another option is to leave battery replacement to a human operator, who can also operate the charging station.

However, this is not the most suitable as drones are mostly employed to increase safety while reducing costs.

A more convenient option is to replace the battery via an automatic station. There are several experimental systems [8], [9] but nowadays also commercial solutions [10], [11], mostly focused on particular drone. So called *drone-in-box* systems is an emerging technology dealing with how to store, deploy from and return to self-contained landing box. It is focused on safety, autonomy, and ease of user accessibility. A few systems even support battery swapping or charging.

Our proposed system, called Droneport (DP), is designed to operate various drones with Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) ability. It is capable of swapping and charging batteries. Unlike the above-mentioned commercial systems, DP will be open-source with published source code for the traffic controller, MAVLink API description, etc.

Swapping and recharging the batteries outside the drone brings fast return to mission. The system is also equipped with a battery management system, considering the storage, battery identification, history and health valuation. Droneport was already introduced in [12] and [13], where the software and simulation tools were described in detail. The rest of the paper deals with the development details of the mechatronic part of DP, focusing on observation regarding the contribution of this tool to the drone or UAV autonomy in general.

II. MECHANICAL DESIGN

Our main goal was to develop a drone Battery management architecture fulfilling a few fundamental objectives:

- battery charging and swapping automatically
- extending the UAV operational time from minutes to hours or more
- MAVLink based data communication standards
- compact and easy handling
- reasonable purchasing/maintenance costs

This has led us to the Droneport architecture as a landing platform covering the charging station and a special manipulator providing the necessary contact and transport connections with the landed drone, see Fig.1.

A. Kinematics and workspace

As mentioned in the previous section, the Droneport includes a special robotic manipulator with a parallelogram structure. This structure is able to reduce the number of

Fig. 1. Droneport concept sketch and CAD overview.

actuators and provide the required manipulation workspace. Compactness and easy handling affect the mechanics significantly.

The manipulator can be divided into three basic mechanical parts:

- H-bot planar moving base - H-bot structure helps to reduce the moving mass by fixing the actuators to the machine support and connecting them to the manipulator via tooth belt, see [14] and Fig.2.
- Parallelogram structured arm - Lightweight planar linkage with parallel structure, driven by a stepper motor with worm wheel gear in the base.
- Battery gripper - Gripper designed to securely attach and detach the battery, transport the battery from and to the charger slots and ensure the connections checks. Section III-A describes the gripper in detail.

Such a system mechanics has a large reach to weight ratio, it means ability to fold itself to the Droneport box, but also be able to reach for the battery over the landed drone. Kinematics of such a manipulator can be described as relation between joint space coordinates $(\alpha_1(t), \alpha_2(t), \varphi(t), \theta(t))^T$ and workspace coordinates $(x(t), y(t), z(t), \psi(t))^T$ in the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} x(t) \\ y(t) \\ z(t) \\ \psi(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{r}{2}(\alpha_1(t) + \alpha_2(t)) \\ \frac{r}{2}(-\alpha_1(t) + \alpha_2(t)) + p_2 - p_1 \sin(\varphi(t)) \\ -p_3 + p_1 \cos(\varphi(t)) \\ k\theta(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where r is radius of belt pulley in H-bot, k is gear ratio between orientation of gripper ψ and its actuator θ , and p_1, p_2, p_3 are parameters of manipulator as depicted in Fig.3. For the tilt angle $\varphi(t)$ from range $(-100^\circ, 100^\circ)$, there exist two solutions converging to one in the upright position. The Jacobian matrix

$$\dot{X}(t) = J(Q)\dot{Q}(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \\ \dot{y}(t) \\ \dot{z}(t) \\ \dot{\psi}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{r}{2} & \frac{r}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{r}{2} & \frac{r}{2} & -p_1 \cos(\varphi(t)) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -p_1 \sin(\varphi(t)) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\alpha}_1(t) \\ \dot{\alpha}_2(t) \\ \dot{\varphi}(t) \\ \dot{\theta}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

defines this singularity, which has to be overcome via motion in jointspace. Workspace can be described in an x-z plane as a polygon with boundaries which are given by reach limits and structure collisions. This polygon is relevant at each shift in the y-axis and all ψ orientations. The Jacobian also defines the relation between motion differences in joints and end effector respectively

$$\delta_X = J(Q)\delta_Q. \quad (4)$$

It is important to verify the impact of worm wheel backlash on the end effector position error. The following graphs (Fig. 4, 5) illustrate the dependence of those motion differences in the workspace for 1° backlash in tilt angle φ .

It results in the main factor influencing the manipulator's accuracy. The belt tension, bearings clearance and material rigidity are in comparison to gear clearance neglected.

B. Dynamics and system inaccuracy

Although the speed of the manipulator movement is not limiting in this case, there are a few reasons to look at the system dynamics. First, the maximal manipulator load is a crucial parameter to deal with. As the Droneport is designed for drones with standard battery packs weighing up to hundreds of grams, we have to design the force-torque relations to raise the battery case in the whole workspace. Moreover, pulling out the battery case from the battery slot, where the contact friction is a main additional force to gravity, must be considered.

The dynamic behavior can be from the essence of the solved problem decoupled to H-bot dynamics and arm dynamics. The H-bot dynamics is driven by stepper motors, where the transformation from rotational motion of the shaft pulleys to the planar motion of the base plate is linear. Assuming the H-bot ensures the movement of the manipulator in an almost horizontal plane, then its actuators produce maximal motion speed and force in that plane about $v_{max} = 3$ [m/s], $F_{max} = 60$ [N], which is far beyond the scope of the required dynamics for the given robot weight.

Arm dynamics can be described as a simplified parallelogram model depicted in Fig. 3, together with dynamics

$$\ddot{\varphi}(t) = \frac{\tau_1 + \tau_{ext} + g(m_1 + m_2)p_1 \sin(\varphi(t))}{(2m_1 + m_2)p_1^2}, \quad (5)$$

where m_1 is a mass of the first linkage, m_2 is a mass of the second linkage with gripper and maximum considered battery load, g is gravity acceleration facing down along the $-z$ axis, τ_1 and τ_{ext} are actuator torque and external parasitic torque respectively.

The design of static load characteristic is based on the previous equation with the assumption of no motion in the system resulting in the expression

$$\tau_1 = -\tau_{ext} - g(m_1 + m_2)p_1 \sin(\varphi(t)), \quad (6)$$

which manages, together with proper estimation of parasitic influences, the design and choice of actuators, load cells, manipulator parts and used materials.

This simple kinematic and dynamic investigations also result in necessity to add some additional sensors and choose control strategies carefully to provide required accuracy for battery gripper positioning. First, the vertical distance is measured directly via an external distance sensor, because the gear backlash limits the precise measurement through the motor encoder. Secondly, the gripper holder contains two load cells used for vertical force control and side force control while pushing and pulling the battery holder to drone or charging slots. It is also beneficial to stay in one of the kinematic solutions because it eliminates the wobbling over the upright position. Moreover two mentioned kinematic solutions

Fig. 2. H-bot kinematic principle.

Fig. 3. Droneport manipulator with battery gripper.

have very different dynamics, which should be controlled differently. So moving to another kinematic solution would result to control for example via gain scheduling, which always brings more complexity to the control loops.

III. BATTERY TRANSPORTATION AND GRIPPING

This section deals with the transportation of the battery between Droneport charging slots and drone battery slot. There are two main goals to deal with. First, there is a problem with standardization of batteries and their connections. Second, ways of precise and secure gripping of the battery by the robot arm together with reconnecting of high current connectors are examined.

Fig. 4. End effector position error w.r.t gear Backlash - y axis.

Fig. 5. End effector position error w.r.t gear Backlash - z axis.

A. Battery case and holder

The approach is to design a special case for a standard Li-Po battery, which can be easily replaced when needed. The standard battery connector for this size of batteries is XT-60, which is reliable and capable of high currents. Unfortunately, it is challenging to connect and reconnect this connector manually, let alone automated by a robot. Therefore designing a unique battery case and holder for a standard Li-Po battery is a way to progress.

Assume the drone battery is placed on top of the drone body, so the gripper jaws can operate over that part to find the battery case position to grab it. The case contains the battery slot, the two alignment pin holes, two levers for gripping and two types of connections. The spring pin connector for monitoring the cells and some other diagnostic purposes, and conductive plates for high power distribution. These two conductive lines and spring pin connector fit securely to custom design battery holder with conductive complement in the form of 2x30 pins spring connector. Disconnection is provided via mentioned levers driven by gripper jaws. The only horizontal force is needed to disconnect the electrical connection. It also releases the battery case from holder, which is then free to pull up from alignment pins. A couple of springs in the battery case realize the necessary contact force for high power distribution during flight. This part has been tested for a 60Amp continuous current. Fig. 6 shows the battery case and holder, which also includes some safety features like polarity control, short circuit

Fig. 6. Battery case and holder.

protection due to improper handling etc.

Thanks to 3D printing, we are able to customize this case and holder parts for every similar drone size. An ArUco code as a unique ID of the holder is used for drone/battery recognition and visual targeting.

B. Gripper

A gripper was designed as a complementary part of the battery holder. The whole gripper body consists of several parts, marked in Fig. 8.

In the front, there are six limit switches/end stops (1), that are used as indicators of battery position. End stops are installed on two gripper jaws (4) operated by a small servo motor (3). For linear movement of jaws, a linear bearings are used. The webcam (2) is used for ArUco code searching and estimation of the battery holder position with respect to the manipulator. The gripper also uses built-in Arduino Micro (5), which is responsible for reading inputs from limit switches/end stops (1) and also controls a small servo motor (3). Connection to the main computer is provided via serial communication over USB. For this sake, a custom control block that performs this operation automatically was also designed, see Fig. 7.

IV. DRONEPORT CONTROL

The DP consists of several components controlled using a single-board computer (UpBoard UP Xtreme with Intel Core i3 processor). The computer uses Debian based Linux OS with real-time kernel capabilities. The REXYGEN by REX Controls company [15] was chosen as a real-time control system for the whole application. The computer is interconnected with the following components, also depicted in Fig. 9:

- **manipulator drives** via CAN Open communication,
- **gripper** via serial line communication over USB,
- **gripper camera** via USB communication,
- **battery charger** via serial line communication over USB,

Fig. 7. Gripper SW driver scheme.

Fig. 8. Bottom and side view of the gripper.

- **additional DI/DO** via real-time EtherCAT gateway,
- **Droneport interface** via MAVLink communication protocol over Ethernet using UDP packets.

Fig. 9. Schematic connection of the control computer with rest of the system.

The control system is developed using function block diagrams in REXYGEN. It is divided into several real-time tasks which are running with different periods. In parallel, there is a standalone application for image processing from the gripper camera written in Python and OpenCV. The data connection between the standalone application and the main control algorithm is done via UDP packets over MAVLink protocol. For example, the wrapper of the MAVLink interface for image processing app communication is shown in Fig. 10.

The control system can be divided into two parts. The first part is responsible for the control of low-level functions such as manipulator movements, communication with the charger, controlling the lit, etc. The second part is a high-level

Fig. 10. Wrapper for image processing.

Fig. 11. Functional block diagram: Path planning program blocks.

controller / program, which is used for orchestrating all the actions. One can imagine this high level control as an oriented graph. Each *node* represents a set of parameters for multiple low-level tasks. For example, position of the lit, position of the manipulator, state of the battery holders, etc. Selected nodes are interconnected via a *path*. Each *path* represents a set of nodes and transitions. Obviously, the next *node* is always started whenever the previous one was successfully done. The parameters for the *nodes* and the description of *paths* are stored in one JSON file.

As shown in Fig. 11 the file is processed via Program block. Whenever some *node* or *path* is started, the current node is processed via ATMT_node (Finite-state automaton) block. This block interprets a sequential function chart (SFC), which check preconditions for the selected *node*, runs the *node* and waits for the result. Each set of parameters in the selected *node* are processed in parallel by suitable subsystem. For example the subsystem for processing the simple Wait (one parameter t_{sec} – for how long should this *node* wait) node is depicted in Fig. 12. Each subsystem has a similar interface. There is an ATMT block for SFC processing, special subsystem for parsing nodes parameters and standardized input/output interface. Whenever the node is executed the ATMT block checks if the parameters are valid, then starts the activity and waits for the result, in this case when the t_{sec} time pass. Then the *DONE* signal is set. In case of error, the *ERR* output is set and the ATMT state remain in error until the node resets. The whole control structure of Droneport is very complex and far beyond the space of this paper. It is assumed to present some detailed information about high and low lever command and control subsystems in the forthcoming paper. The current version of the prototype is depicted in Fig. 13.

Fig. 12. Simple example of wait node.

Fig. 13. Current version of the Droneport prototype with landed drone.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper described the Droneport system with an emphasis on mechanics and hardware. First, the concept of the whole system was outlined and defined with respect to state of the art in this AUV branch. Next, the key HW components were described together with their functionality, benefits and limitations. Future work on the Droneport system will cover extending the traffic control with a time-scheduler for optimal utilization of the entire system. According to general public demands, it seems beneficial to extend the manipulator functionality with the possibility of exchanging tools of payloads between the drone and the Droneport. These extension possibilities and limitations are part of future discussions and Droneport research.

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